

A STUDY ON STRESS MANAGEMENT AT THE WORKPLACE WITH RESPECT TO HUMAN RESOURCE POLICIES WITHIN AN ORGANIZATION.

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ABSTRACT:

The study focuses on the subject "a study on stress management at the workplace, with respect to human resource policies within an organization", The study's objectives were to find the stress level of employee's in the organization, the causes of stress, Stress can have an impact on a person's health, productivity at work, social life, and family relationships. The stressors and their consequences must be understood at individual and organizational levels. To find and understand the relationship between stress and various other factors in human resource policies. To promote interactivity in internal information flow and create a healthy organizations! personnel structure, human resource managers are crucial in the development of stress management solutions. Through this study article, an effort has been made to understand the sources of stress among organization employees and the strategies they utilize to manage the stress they experience at work. This paper aims to provide insight that will help the reader further improve his/her management competencies in managing stress in the workplace.

Keywords: Stress management, Productivity, Stress, Employee, Workplace

INTRODUCTION:

The Latin word "strictus" (which meaning "to tighten") is where the word "stress" originates. According to one definition of stress, it is a state of high emotional or physical tension that develops as a result of various life conditions or events and can lead to feelings like rage, irritation, panic, worry, or, in certain cases, determination to overcome a task. However, there are tools, methods, tactics, or other approaches that may be used to manage stress, so it is not uncontrollable. Stress management is what we call this. A technique for reducing stress or controlling a person's level of stress with the goal of enhancing daily activities and performance is known as stress management.

External causes like technological development and change in a nation's economy are also contributing to an increase in workplace stress. Multinational corporations, whose employees come from many cultural backgrounds and whose operations are conducted globally, are likewise prone to experiencing stress. Aside from stress that may result from personal or family issues, stress at work has become a bigger issue as a result of employment reorganization, globalization, and increased demand for the task at hand. Employees could feel stressed and distressed as a result of increased job uncertainty. Tennant (2002), page 697 We became intrigued, sensitive, and curious about the significance of the topic as a result of the growing employee stress.

It is the susceptibility to stress rather than stress itself that causes mental instability. "A study made by the Institute of Psychiatry found that people with high-stress jobs have twice the risk of developing serious depression or anxiety compared with others in less stressful occupations."

(Melchior et al., 2007, p.2) Employees can experience work stress regardless of their gender, job title, or industry. Looking around and reading the data on stress, particularly workplace stress, reveals that stress is accepted by employees as an unavoidable aspect. When performing an activity, stress is related to one's capacity to manage resources, environmental demands, and some other unidentified flaws in the process; yet, if the subject appears to be general in nature, then it would be seen as an unpredictable phenomenon.

If stress is not well managed, it can cause illness and increase the number of sick days that employees take, which has a direct correlation to the business world. As a result, it will have an impact on both the company and its personnel. However, some degree of tension in the workplace might inspire workers to put in extra effort and boost productivity. Both the person and the business are negatively impacted by stress that puts an employee under enough strain that they are unable to handle the issue. (CIPD, 2008, p. 2) The effects of stress on an organization's performance are severe. An organization may experience higher staff churn, employee absence, and decreased productivity as a result of stress. Stress has a financial impact on firms as well. Sick leave is typically the most evident and straightforward expense to measure. (CIPD, 2008, p. 3). Therefore, it is important to emphasize that stress will cause a business to incur higher costs.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Everybody goes through times of stress in their lives. The main focus of the company should be on stress management while ensuring that no harm happens to the employees. Because it is simple for stressed employees to lose concentration and for their emotions to spread and affect the other employees through their behaviors due to the influence of being in stressful situations, it is imperative to have an efficient stress management strategy in place.

Conflict and distraction at work are results of work stress. If the workload is too heavy, they are unable to perform their jobs effectively. If they aren't assigned tasks they can do or aren't given the proper training, both the employees and the company will be unhappy. Depression, anxiety,

trouble sleeping, trouble coping with work, and a decline in work performance are all brought on by the workplace. Organizations must recognize that stress is a health and safety issue, and stress management strategies must be put in place to identify and control stress,

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- . To research the factors that contribute to employee stress related to HR policies.
- . To know the level of stress on employees at the workplace.
- . To analyze the importance of interventional strategies to manage stress within an organization employees.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study is to evaluate the organization's human resource policy in relation to the study on stress management at work. This study will aid in identifying the methods and resources for stress management as well as the numerous stressors in our environment and how to manage them. This study will demonstrate that stress can be both good and bad-even a little bit of it can motivate people to perform their jobs more effectively. While stress in the workplace cannot be completely removed, a healthy amount has positive effects. Finally, there is a thin line between being enough stressed to carry out one's responsibilities and being harmfully stressed to the point where it causes you to lose focus.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In their investigation, Holyroyd and Lazarus explained in 1982 that "psychological stress requires a judgment that environmental and/or internal demands exceed the individual's resources for managing them".

In contrast, Selye (1976) defined stress as a demand, threat, or other incident that forces a person to cope. He went on to say that the interference or strain that prevents an organism from functioning normally. When this is in effect, the person may notice weakness and unexplained or unidentified discomfort, as well as sleep and food disorders ..

As stated by Cox (1993), "stress is now understood as a psychological state that results from people's perceptions of an imbalance between job demands and their abilities to cope with those demands'. A further definition is _work stress is a psychological state which can cause an individual to behave dysfunction ally at work and results from people's response to an imbalance between job demands and their abilities to cope".

Fundamentally, workplace stress arises when people try to cope with tasks, responsibilities or other forms of pressure connected with their jobs, but encounter difficulty, strain, anxiety and worry in endeavoring to cope. Bechr and Newman (1978) perceived stress in an occupational setting to mean a condition where in job related factors interact with workers, to change their psychological and physiological conditions such that the person's mind and body are forced to deviate from normal functioning.

Formulation of Research Problem:

An individual's health can be affected by the positive and negative stress initiated by an event. The Implication of a significant incident like winning one million dollars from the lottery or a successful happy engagement can cause positive stress and negative events can have negative effects of can hurt a person's health. Negative events such as dying of a close member of the family or the decline of the financial situation of a person can affect a person in a negative way. (Anderson & Amoult, 1989, p. 102)

The absence of an adequate leadership can also cause conflict between the employers and employees, it also indicates as a source of stress within an organization. Typically, the activities on a board ship like organizing of teamwork is marked as a usual process and not related to stress under normal situations. Whereas working in an isolated environment can also cause discomfort among the employees. Capsule environment refers to a community which is remote from home, families and friends; this creates stress because of lack of security in one's life where loved ones and friends are not close. (Fairbrother, & Warn, 2003 p. 10).

(Agolla & Ongori, 2009, p. 64) In order to discuss stress in the form of emotions, we can see that emotions are related to a subjective trait of an individual's feelings or moods. Emotions create specific feelings to an individual like happiness, shame or anger. The other side of emotions is related to sentiment and temper which comes out of emotion and leads to stress. (Ashforth & Humphrey, 1995, p. 99) If stress is defined as per the emotions perspective we see that there is not a definite definition for emotions available in the literatures; two reasons stated as to why

there is no definite definition of emotions is that first, emotion is a broadly used term; next, emotions are described as a subjective feature of an individual's feelings and moods. Therefore, scholars think about emotions in many different ways. The situation, period, level and consistency of an individual's sentiment are different from person to person. Typically, emotion are used in various forms such as social emotion which states the feelings of an individual like filling happy, joyous, shame, affection etc.

Tips for Stress Management:

A The American Psychological Association offers seven suggestions that have been modified to help people with stress management plans:

1. Recognize your stress

What causes you stress? Everyone may experience it differently. Knowing how you react to stress will help you be more prepared and use your stress-reduction tools as needed.

2. Determine your sources of stress

What makes you stressed out? Work, family, transition, or any of the other thousands of potential triggers could be the cause.

3. Acquire the ability to spot stress signs.

It's crucial to recognize your stress symptoms, because everyone processes stress differently. What internal alarms are you hearing? Low tolerance for stress, headaches, stomachaches, or a mix of the aforementioned "Symptoms of Stress".

4. Recognize your coping mechanisms for stress

What method do you usually use to relax? These may be taught behaviors that occasionally aren't the best course of action. For instance, some people self-medicate with alcohol or overindulge to deal with stress.

5. Use beneficial stress reduction techniques

It's wise to be aware of any unhealthy coping mechanisms you may be using so you may replace them with healthier alternatives. For instance, if overeating is now your go-to behavior, you can choose to try meditation instead or decide to call a buddy to talk through your dilemma. According to the American Psychological Association, altering one behavior at a time is the most efficient way to bring about good change.

6. Prioritize taking care of oneself.

We prioritize our own needs over those of others when we make time for ourselves. Although at first this may seem self-centered, it is similar to the flight analogy in that we must put our own oxygen mask on before helping others. The most basic factors that contribute to wellbeing, like getting adequate sleep, eating healthily, relaxing, and exercising, are frequently neglected.

7. When assistance is required, ask for it.

Contact a friend or family member you can chat to if you're feeling overwhelmed. Speaking with a healthcare professional can also help us acquire better coping mechanisms and reduce stress.

Human Resource Policies within an Organization

HR policies are a set of guidelines and rules created by an organization to govern the behavior, decision-making, and actions of its employees. These policies cover a wide range of topics related to employee management and are designed to ensure fairness, compliance with laws and regulations, and consistency across the organization. Some common HR policies include:

Code of Conduct:

It outlines ethical standards and expected behavior for employees.

- Attendance Policy: It defines expectations for punctuality, absences, and leaves of absence.
- Equal Employment Opportunity Policy: It ensures non-discrimination and equal opportunities for all employees.
- Harassment and Anti-Bullying Policy: It prohibits any form of harassment or bullying in the workplace.
- Compensation and Benefits Policy: It outlines the company's compensation structure, pay scale, and employee benefits.
- Performance Management Policy: It details the process of setting performance goals, conducting performance reviews, and career development.
- Leave Policy: It covers various types of leaves, such as vacation, sick leave, maternity/paternity leave, and bereavement leave.
- Internet and Social Media Policy: It governs employees' use of company technology and guidelines for social media usage.
- Health and Safety Policy: It outlines safety guidelines and procedures to ensure a safe working environment.
- Grievance and Conflict Resolution Policy: It provides a mechanism for employees to raise concerns and resolve conflicts in the workplace.

These policies help organizations maintain a positive work culture, comply with employment laws, and foster a productive and inclusive work environment.

Importance of stress management to employees' performance:

- . It improves performance and productivity
- . It promotes ethical behaviour among employees
- . It helps reduce conflict in the organizations
- . Employees have clear minds to perform their duties
- . It provides a healthy work environment with the help of team members,
- . Increases the chances of meeting deadlines

Role of HR Policies in managing stress at the workplace:

For managers to successfully run a department and increase productivity and revenue, they must comprehend the importance of an employee's mental wellness. Managers can use the five action-oriented steps presented in Figure 1 by the World Health Organization to implement certain recommendations made for the prevention of work-related stress.

Figure: 1. Process of Stress Prevention Source: World Health Organization

There are some important roles and responsibilities that an HR manager needs to do in stress management (Balaji, 2014):

1. Identify types of stress in the workplace.
2. Understand the reasons which lead to stress at the workplace.
3. Ask employees: What solutions can be taken to prevent these stresses?
4. Build policies about stress management appropriately and effectively to handle stress in the company.
5. Discuss and engage with the staff about the problems of stress, and enhance their awareness of the method of working or other related aspects.
6. Perform management standards well to determine the level of stress, and what approaches might be applied to solve the current circumstance.
7. Discuss with other departments in building and applying the resolutions.
8. Observe and adjust stress management methods following company policies and procedures.
9. Coordinate with managers to promptly detect and help employees who are under stress.
10. Establish sustainable policies that can improve employees' welfare and health.

Throughout the process of planning and implementing the stress-reducing policies, HR managers need to clarify, explain and provide guidance for managers from other departments to ensure the intended results. Through development programs for managers and leaders, HR Policies play & critical role in monitoring the efficacy of conflict resolution strategies, training employees or identifying and managing stress, and providing ongoing support to managers and staff in & changing environment.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

How do businesses recognize and address employee stress related to internal human resource policies?

What resources are available to develop an efficient stress management plan?

Hypothesis of the Study

The hypothesis for the study is as follows:

H1: Age and stress levels do not correlate with one another.

H2: Gender and levels of stress are not correlated.

H3: HR policies and stress levels do not correlate with one another.

H4: There is no connection between HR policies and stress-related factors.

DATA COLLECTION OF THE STUDY

The collection of primary and secondary data will serve as the foundation for the current investigation. The sample Size is 70. Primary data was collected through a self-structured questionnaire from the employees. Books, internet websites, journals, etc were used as a source of secondary data. ANOVA, Correlation, and Chi-square techniques were used to analyze and interpret results to achieve research objectives,

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS:

Table 1. Correlation Test on Relationship between Age and Stress Level

Correlations		What is your Age Category?	If yes, rate of Stress levels.
What is your Age Category?	Pearson Correlations	1	-0.22
	Sig.(1-tailed)		0.436
	N	70	70
If yes, rate of Stress levels.	Pearson Correlations	-0.22	1
	Sig.(1-tailed)	0.436	
	N	70	70

Interpretation :

The observed significance level 0.436 is greater than 0.05 thus the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Age and Stress level is accepted and the Alternative hypothesis is rejected.

The correlation coefficient is -0.22, there is a slight negative relationship between age and stress level.

Table 2 : ANOVA Test on Relationship between Gender and Levels of Stress

Source	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F	Pr > F
Model	1	0.199	0.199	1.420	0.248
Error	69	8.134	0.140		
Corrected	70	8.333			

Interpretation

The observed significance level (0.248) is greater than 0.05 thus the null hypothesis that there is no relationship between Gender and Levels of Stress is accepted and the alternate hypothesis is rejected.

Table3. Correlation test on relationship between stress levels and Human Resource policies.

Correlations		If yes, rate of the stress levels?	Human Resource Policies for employees?
If yes, rate of the stress levels?	Pearson Correlations	1	.092
	Sig.(1-tailed)		0.238
	N	70	70
Human Resource Policies for employees?	Pearson Correlations	.092	1
	Sig.(1-tailed)	0.238	
	N	70	70

Interpretation:

The observed significance level (0.238) is greater 0.05 thus the null hypothesis that there is no relationship between stress levels and HR policies is true, and the opposing theory is disproven.

The correlation coefficient is -0.092, there is a slight negative relationship between age and stress level.

Table 4. ANOVA test on the relationship between Human Resource policies and stress related factors.

Source	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F	Pr > F
Model	1	0.368	0.368	1.458	0.507
Error	69	46.615	0.804		
Corrected	70	46.983			

Interpretation:

The observed significance level (0.507) is greater than 0.05 thus the null hypothesis that there is no relationship between HR Policies and Stress related factors are accepted and the alternate hypothesis is rejected.

FINDINGS:

Employees think that the management has not taken efforts to reduce their stress levels. This can cause serious problems to the organization because stress can affect the work performance of the employees which in turn will affect their productivity.

As shown in the data analysis, employees face difficulties that cause stress these include; Age, Gender, organizational policies, excessive interruptions, lack of recognition, shortage of required resources, continuous, and chaotic job demands and shortage of help at work. The above-mentioned issues are what cause stress in employees because they occur in the workplace which are not being addressed. Workplace stress can be brought on by the workload of employees such as the ones above and this shows itself in different ways which can therefore affect the overall performance of employees and the organization as a whole.

Stress is influenced by various factors in our workplace and that it affects job performance. This goes to show that the issue of stressed employees will never end and organizations should implement strategies to handle it and reduce stressful situations in their organization. The research revealed that organizations do not have stress management facilities, policies, or strategies in place. Employees do not utilize any stress management. Having a strategy in place is purely for the benefit and growth of the organization.

CONCLUSION

Organizations should be a watchdog in the stress management process, treat all employees equally regardless of their age, gender, experience, income, or any other priority, and use business tactics to manage without any dissatisfaction. Stress management is a leading fact that every organization should concentrate on so that they can keep an eye on their performance and productivity. Stress may have negative repercussions on both an individual's health and the health of the company when employees put themselves under excessive strain at work by setting lofty expectations. Employee stress can be managed by proper time management, and seeking help from Human Resource Management Policies. Emotion-focused strategies like leisure activities, companionship, and exercise can also be used to relieve stress. As a result, the research offered several suggestions and highlighted how human resources policy might help to reduce workplace stress.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

Organizations ought to put more emphasis on employee work-life balance and take the initiative to put these tactics into practice. Flexible work schedules should be offered to employees as this will greatly lessen their stress.

Employees who perform should be recognized, there should be an appropriate and effective performance evaluation and appraisal. Management should be able to identify good work and motivate employees.

Organizations should take up the initiative to have stress management strategies, policies, and facilities in to workplace to handle stress and maintain good work balance and cooperation.

We also recommend that sharing our Idea and problems helps to provide solutions so therefore this also helps in minimizing stress. Therefore sharing stressful situations with others, and sharing feelings and emotions as much as possible contributes to relieving stress and making an employee better off both at his work and in his personal life.

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